

ETYMOLOGICAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT “HAPPINESS”-“BAXT” IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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***Annotation:** In this article, a comparative analysis of the etymological and semantic aspects of the concept of happiness in English and Uzbek, as well as the traditions and mentality of representatives of two unrelated languages. The article also provides a comparative analysis of dictionaries, proverbs and examples from fiction, which are available in two languages.*

***Keywords:** Feeling, trust, love, attitude, jealousy, culture, divine, eternal, satisfaction, sadness, rival, betrayal, conscience, gesture.*

INTRODUCTION

As we know, happiness is one of the fundamental concepts of human life. Regardless of the nationality, race, or beliefs of a person, this concept means a certain fullness of being, the ultimate goal of the individual. Of course, each person interprets and associates it with different values in their own way. Therefore, I think it would be interesting to compare the etymology and semantics of this concept in

unrelated languages, that is, the material of the English and Uzbek languages.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

So, let's look at the concept of happiness first in English. Although it is independent in meaning, yet this concept is inextricably linked with such concepts as love, joy, friendship. As is clear from the etymological dictionaries of the English language,

the word happiness is a noun with the root hap (event, luck) and is borrowed from the Old Norse language¹. All explanatory dictionaries of the English language indicate that this lexeme is created by means of the adjective happy and suffixes: happiness. In particular, in the dictionaries “Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary”, “New Oxford – New Oxford Dictionary of English” the following meanings of the lexeme are indicated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Happy – feeling or expressing pleasure, contentment, bakhtdan mamnunlik khissi: you don’t look very happy today; I won't be happy until I know she is safe;

Happy - felling satisfied that smth is good, right etc, that is, a sense of satisfaction: I'm not happy with his work this term;

Happy - in greeting, full of joy, that is, a sense of self-realization, pleasure: birthday, happychristmas;

Happy - to do smth. Pleased or very willing to do smth, that is, a sense of accomplishment of "duty": I am (more than) happy to be of service;

Happy - fortunate, lucky, that is, feeling of luck, prospects: He is in the happy position of never having or worry about money;

Happy - (of words, ideas, behavior etc.) well suited to the situation, pleasing; not a very happy choice of words/combo of colors. A happy event, the happy golden /many happy returns etc.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word bakht is given the following description. It is borrowed from the Persian language, and originally meant a share, a lot, an inheritance, a share. At the same time, this word over time began to mean satisfaction with one's activity, success, lifestyle, fulfillment of desires, achievement of a goal, that is, such concepts that are closer to moral, moral values. Let's turn to examples.

¹ Concise Dictionary of English Etymology.W.W.Skeat. - Wordsworth Editions Limited, 2007. - 648p.

Complete satisfaction with your life: *Ona-yer nafasiga, mehriga, in'omlariga to'yib yashashdan ortiq baxt bormi? – Saodat.*

At the same time, this lexeme also has such semantic synonyms as *omad, tole, iqbol: Nega boshingga qo'ngan baxt qushni kaltak olib quvlaysan?*²

The following synonyms of the concept of “baxt” can be given: *saodat, omad, shodlik, xursandchilik, iqbol, mamnunlik, baxtiyorlik, tole, murod, niyat, qobil.*

In the explanatory dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language, Azim Khozhiev (“O‘zbek tili sinonimlarning izohli lug‘ati”), the word “*baxt*” and its synonyms are interpreted as follows: *baxt, iqbol, tole, saodat* are synonyms and express a sense of satisfaction with life, or something that gives a person such a feeling³. The synonym *iqbol* is typical mainly for the high style. With the synonyms *tole, baxt, iqbol*, the variant *omad* coincides most of all in meaning. The synonym *saodat* is characteristic

of the literary language and is used less frequently. There are also such synonyms as *baxtli, baxtiyor, saodatli, toleli, mas'ud: Baxtiyor bo'lgan, baxtikulgan. Saodatli kitob. Baxtli ko'zim, men o'ylab boqsam, Ikki bahor ko'ribdi yoshing.* The synonym *mas'ud* is now considered obsolete and is characteristic of high style.

CONSLUSION

Thus, we can conclude that, firstly, the concept of happiness in both languages is fundamental when a person evaluates his life, his being.

Secondly, the linguistic cultural idea of happiness is an ethnocentric semantic structure that determines the national identity of a person.

Thirdly, the concept of happiness, as an axiological mental unit of the language image of the world, offers the following basic (central) ideas: “favor of fate”; “luck”, “intense joy”; “positive balance of life”, “satisfaction with life”. With the concept of misfortune, such feelings as “failure”, “grief”, “hard case”,

² Karamatova K., Karamatov H.S. Proverbs, Makollar, Proverbs. - T.: Mehnat, 2010. - 398 p.

³ Khozhiev A. Uzbek tili synonymarining isohli lugati. - T.: Uqituvchi, 2014. - 307 p.

“trouble”, “mental anguish” are associated.

Fourthly, the idea of happiness has a historically evolutionary and changeable character; this is also confirmed in texts of a different nature belonging to different eras.

Fifthly, when comparing the concepts of happiness and unhappiness in both languages, there is also a similarity at the level of proverbs and phraseological units.

Sixth, the main differences between the concepts are in dictionary definitions.

Seventh, the ethnocultural idea of happiness is primarily focused on the basic semantics of the concept of happiness. It depends on everyday views of existence in the society of happiness and unhappiness.

So, happiness in both languages is a kind of fundamental concept, the most important value for the individual and is found in the spheres of society.

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